

The Basis of Biological Mechanisms Underlying Mobility

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<https://sites.google.com/view/barredowlscrime>

The actual mechanism that translates to effector processes can be hidden or more so, far removed from the chain of cause and effect. The purpose of movement in biological entities might be much more than simple food/ nutrient access or resource acclimatization. Acclimatization because resources become fuel/ utilities, and any source of fuel or utility is only so when internal and external variables adjust, alter or adapt to its characteristics and effects can be harnessed. Resource acclimatization is much larger than say resource acquisition or utilization. In a similar vein, mobility might actually be an adjustment to internal or external factors based on other parameters such as organismic mass, fluid flow characteristics, substance hotspot delineation etc.

There is a possibility that in humans, while the heart is the source of fluid flow pressure, it is the systemically distributed fluid pressure gradient variegation that is the core reason for the need for movement. Pressure gradients do not establish without inertial differences and when it comes to the human body, boundary conditions need to be periodically 'created' for differentials to be established and if need be, sustained. This conditional dependence is bound to exist for any soft bodied organism that has a partly rigid and specifically patterned constitutional infrastructure.

This would mean that mobility serves a far greater structural purpose than usually thought of. Any intentional or purposeful activity executed by biological organisms would then be secondary to the mobility provided maintenance of structural integrity.